

E-Commerce – A Tool for Sustainable Business Development

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Research Topic

This research paper is about E-Commerce, its differences from Traditional commerce and how it is a tool for Sustainable Business Development

Introduction

Innovation in technology and communication has brought significant changes in the ways of conducting a business. The invention of Internet especially has helped economies to grow significantly due to the rapid growth of e-commerce. Bloomenthal in a web article of Investopedia titled "E-Commerce (e-commerce)" states that "E-Commerce or Electronic Commerce is a business model that lets firms and individuals conduct business over electronic networks, most notably: the Internet." Wikipedia further elaborates that "Electronic commerce draws on technologies such as mobile commerce, electronic funds transfer, supply chain management, Internet marketing, online transaction processing, electronic data interchange (EDI), inventory management systems and automated data collection systems."

E-Commerce in Market Segments

E-commerce currently operates in all four of the following major market segments:

1. Business to Business e-commerce (B2B): B2B e-commerce is the sale of goods and services between businesses using online sales portal. It is used by businesses to improve selling and acquiring raw materials and products which are used to provide finished goods. It helps businesses to reduce overhead costs.
2. Business to Consumer e-commerce (B2C): B2C e-commerce is a business model that enables businesses to sell their goods or services to the final and individual consumers using portals and websites. It helps businesses to sell their products over a large geographical area without having to invest and diversify by the means of franchises or outlets. Best examples of B2C websites are Amazon, Alibaba, Flipkart, etc.
3. Consumer to Consumer e-commerce (C2C): C2C e-commerce is a business model that helps consumers to interact in a market using e-commerce. In this market, consumers sell each other goods or

services by the means of websites like eBay, Quiclr, etc.

4. Consumer to Business e-commerce (C2B): C2B e-commerce is a reverse form of traditional business where consumers offer goods or services to businesses. In other words, it refers to consumers who create value and businesses consume this value. One of the examples for C2B e-commerce is consumers offering reviews and suggestions to businesses using portals and businesses adopts these suggestions.

Objectives

- To study the difference between traditional business and e-commerce.
- To study the role played by e-commerce in different aspects of channels of distribution.
- To study the reasons behind how E-Commerce makes business development sustainable.

Traditional Commerce vs. e-Commerce

- Commerce focuses mainly on the exchange of goods and services and all activities that encourage trade and exchange. On the other hand, E-commerce refers to transactions or exchange of goods, services or information communicated electronically.
- The exchange of goods and services for money or credit can take place only during business hours in traditional commerce whereas, in E-commerce, the transactions can take place at any time.
- The geographical scope/extent of traditional business is limited to a particular region of operation. On the contrary, businesses using E-commerce have better reach to consumers spread over a wide geographical area due to its ease of access.
- Traditional commerce involves the physical inspection of goods before purchasing them, whereas it is not the case in E-commerce because there is no physical interaction between the buyer and the seller.
- E-Commerce enables the buyers to return the goods as it does not involve a physical inspection. On the other hand, as the buyers can inspect the goods before purchase, it does not offer much scope to return the product.
- Unlike E-Commerce, traditional businesses have to rely on intermediaries for information about the market. Businesses using e-commerce can acquire information using the Internet, which reduces the dependency on intermediaries.
- Traditional business has less scope for advertising according to consumer's preferences as they have only one way of marketing their products. E-commerce analyses the interests of a particular consumer and offers him the same.
- The delivery of goods is immediate and direct in the case of traditional commerce but is delayed in e-commerce. On the other hand, the product is delivered directly to the consumer's choice of place in the case of e-commerce.
- In traditional commerce, transactions are made through cash, cheques or credit facilities like credit cards, etc. But e-commerce involves no movement of cash physically but instead is transferred electronically with the help of credit cards, fund transfers, etc. E-commerce also makes it easier to transact larger sums of money electronically rather than having to withdraw large sums of money as cash.
- In traditional business, all transactions are processed manually whereas, in e-commerce, all transactions are processed electronically.

Table 1: Global Market Size of Retail Industry vs. E-Commerce (in US\$ trillions)

Year	Retail Industry	% Change	E-Commerce	% Change
2015	21.19	-	1.548	-
2016	22.49	6.13	1.845	19.19
2017	20.8	-7.51	2.304	24.88
2018	22.05	6.01	2.842	23.35
2019	23.45	6.35	3.453	21.50
2020	24.86	6.01	4.135	19.75

From Table 1 and Chart 1, it is observed that in 2015, the global market size of retail industry was estimated at US\$21.19 trillion whereas the market size of e-commerce was estimated at US\$1.548 trillion. It is evident that the market size of retail industry is almost 14 times the market size of e-commerce. Regardless of this huge difference in market sizes, E-Commerce markets grow at an average rate of 21.73% whereas the retail industry grows only at an average of 3.40%. The market size of retail industry in 2020 is forecasted at US\$ 24.86 trillion whereas the market size of e-commerce industry for the same year is forecasted at US\$4.135 trillion. Here, the market size of retail industry is only roughly 6 times the size of e-commerce industry. This shows that the use of e-commerce by both consumers and sellers is increasing rapidly and is soon to compete with the retail industry.

E-Commerce’s effect on Distribution

In commerce, distribution is given by supply chain management. According to the web article titled “Supply Chain Management” given by Wikipedia, Supply chain management refers to “the management of flow of goods and services, involves the movement and storage of raw materials, of work-in-process inventory, and of finished goods from point of origin to point of consumption.” Channels of distribution have been used by businesses traditionally to provide goods and services. The longest channel of distribution is as follows:

Goods produced by companies are bought in large lots by wholesalers, who are helped by certain agents to sell these goods in smaller lots to the retailers, who in turn sell the goods in individual units to the final consumer. With the increase in usage of e-commerce, the channel of distribution

used by businesses that engage in e-commerce has reduced significantly. Instead of using a lengthy channel of distribution which involves agents and retailers, businesses can directly deliver goods over a large geographical area with the help of proper logistics systems. This also significantly reduces the price of the goods sold as agents and retailers do not participate in the channel and increase the price to obtain profits, thus making products more attractive due to less price.

On the other hand, e-commerce has increased the need for proper warehouses and logistics providers. This has resulted in large competition amongst logistics providers as they are required to provide faster delivery, tracking services of the goods, less hassle and better handling of products and better quality of service to the consumers and businesses to survive in the market.

Advantages of E-Commerce over Traditional Business

- There are no geographical boundaries for businesses engaging in E-commerce, hence businesses do not have to invest heavily on expansion and diversification but can use that capital to increase production and can improve the quality of goods and services offered.
- A business engaged in E-commerce can use ‘targeted marketing’ with the help of data collected from search engines like Google, Yahoo!, thus improves branding efficiently ensuring low cost.
- Businesses which use E-commerce require much less initial capital/investment than traditional businesses as there is no investment made in retail units. Businesses only need warehouses which relatively has less cost of functioning in comparison to a retail store. This encourages entrepreneurs to start their businesses with less initial capital and offer their goods or services using E-commerce.
- As there is no involvement of agents or retailers in E-commerce, the businesses can sell the goods and services at discounted prices and increase sales using promotions, offers, etc. Thus, businesses can focus on increasing their profits by selling more quantities rather than exploiting consumers by selling fewer quantities.

Conclusion

“The e-commerce industry is a force that no investor can afford to ignore.”

- Cushla Sherlock

From the above-mentioned points, it is evident that E-Commerce as an innovation is a better tool for sustainable business development. E-Commerce enables businesses regardless of their size to compete in a market that is easily approachable by the direct and final consumers. This research paper believes that E-Commerce will become the norm for the exchange of goods and services in the near future.

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